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General Compliance Analysis of Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552 in the Context of the Paris Agreement and the European Green Deal

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Abstract

Today, global environmental challenges issues including heat waves, extreme rainfall, floods as well as massive forest fires are alarming. Since the Industrial Revolution, these problems have become even more serious. Countries around the world have adopted international and regional legal regulations, such as Conventions, Protocols, and Agreements, that impose obligations and responsibilities on legal states to mitigate global warming and combat climate change. Among these are the Paris Agreement and the European Green Deal (EGD). The Agreement and the Deal have been

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established as international legal instruments aimed at reducing global temperature rise, lowering emission levels to desired targets, promoting green transition, ensuring sustainable production and financing, and providing renewable energy sources. Countries have felt the need to implement national legal regulations to avoid being economically and legally affected by international standards and sanctions imposed on climate action. Turkey has integrated international standards for climate action into its national legal framework by enacting Climate Law No. 7552. This law has established the legal framework for the steps to be taken by institutions and organizations in the country's combating global warming. This study aims in order to evaluate overall legal alignment of Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552 regarding the Agreement and the EGD using qualitative comparative method. Normative legal documents, official websites, academic research, and articles were used for data collection.

Keywords: Paris Agreement, European Green Deal, Turkey Climate Law, Legal Analysis, Climate Change.

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I. Introduction

Since the Industrial Revolution, the world's activities and policies under the guise of economic growth have placed considerable pressure on the environment, leading to the emergence of climate problems. Combating climate change has necessitated not only environmental policies but also the implementation of necessary regulations in economic and legal areas. Climate policies in countries have followed certain global processes, and climate actions have been carried out with the aim of solving a general problem that concerns the world, not a regional problem. While these efforts were initially primarily conducted within the framework of voluntary efforts by governments, the seriousness of the climate change response has led to the adoption of legally binding regulations.

The world has attempted to address the global climate crisis by signing various agreements, protocols, and treaties as part of its climate policies. One such agreement is the Paris Agreement, which came into force in 2015. Because nearly every country in the world has participated in the agreement, it has become the most comprehensive international document. The agreement seeks to cap the global temperature increase at 1.5°C, while also imposing obligations such as voluntary emission reductions by the participating nations as well as monetary support provided by developed nations to those in development.

European Union (EU), a pioneer in tackling environmental issues as well as global warming on the international stage, published the EGD in 2019 to help this continent achieve its goal of climate neutrality by 2050. The agreement, with the accompanying regulations, has introduced a widespread transformation in environmental, economic, social, and political spheres. The agreement has become legally binding with the implementation mechanisms of the *European Union Emissions Trading System* (EU ETS), the *Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism* (CBAM), and the *European Climate Law*. While the agreement applies to member states, its implementation mechanisms have also impacted countries outside the Union. Due to the Union's foreign trade relations with other countries, the regulations have had an impact beyond the continent, with Turkey, its largest export partner, being at the forefront of these countries.

As Turkey is a candidate country for EU membership and its main trading partner, it could not remain indifferent to the EU's climate policies. To reduce greenhouse gas emission levels, promote and increase renewable energy sources, ensure a shift toward a circular economy, and combat climate change, Turkey enacted Law No. 7552 on Climate in 2025 in order to meet both its global and national commitments. The law was developed at the national level in accordance with the EGD agreement and ensured that the country's climate policies were within a legal framework. The law establishes the responsibilities of institutions and organizations, such as establishing a national ETS and CBAM, and monitoring and reporting emissions. Its most important feature is the provision of penal sanctions for parties' failure to fulfill their responsibilities.

Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552 is analyzed in relation to the Paris Agreement and the European Green Deal within a theoretical framework based on the approaches of Polycentric/Bottom-Up Governance, the Union's Regulatory Externality approach together with the Normative Power Europe perspective, national alignment/Europeanization, and legal harmonization frameworks. The Polycentric/Bottom-Up Governance approach; according to Ostrom, the bottom-up governance approach is associated with the polycentric approach, in which decision-making centers include different actors and a system is formed where flexible and inclusive governance mechanisms are established instead of centralized and uniform solutions (Ostrom, 2010, pp. 552–553). The Union's Regulatory Externality approach and the Normative Power Europe perspective; the European Union, particularly by using its trade power, extends its own rules to non-EU countries and influences them, which is defined as the Regulatory Externality approach (Tamim, 2024, pp. 8–9). The Normative Power approach appears as a form of influence based not on military or coercive power, but on norms and ideational foundations (Günay, 2024, pp. 72). The national alignment/Europeanization approach refers to the diffusion of policies, rules, procedures, and practices that are accepted within the Union to other nations, incorporating them into their domestic legislation (Hocaoğlu Bahadır, 2021, pp. 239). Legal harmonization is explained as a process in which national legislation maintains its own characteristics while converging with or adapting to other legal systems (Özdemir, 2017, pp. 159).

This study aims to answer the questions “To what extent is the Turkish Climate Law No. 7552 aligned with the legal principles of the Paris Agreement and the European Green Deal? What are the similarities or differences? What recommendations can be made for regulatory or implementing bodies?” through a comparative legal analysis method.

It is examined particularly in terms of mixed or centralized governance, the impact of international rules on national law, and the principles of just transition and sustainable development within the theoretical framework. By using the fundamental concepts of climate law research, a comparative analysis is conducted on the incorporation of international provisions into national legislation and the contrast between the flexible and voluntary nature of international law and the binding and sanction-based structure of national law. The study identifies the problems clearly so that policymakers and implementing bodies can enhance their climate action strategies. While contributing to the academic literature, the analysis also provides recommendations for regulators and practitioners. At the same time, it brings together the dimensions of legal analysis, governance, financing, and public participation in an integrated manner.

II. Methods

This study compares and evaluates the Turkey Climate Law No. 7552, recently enacted in Turkey, with the Paris Agreement and EGD, focusing on their fundamental principles and legal frameworks. The comparison seeks to highlight similarities, differences, alignments, and potential gaps among these normative legal instruments. A qualitative comparative analysis method was employed for this purpose.

In this context, the comparative criteria were carried out through three main stages. The first concerns the legal fundamental principles and legal framework, including the level of binding force; the second concerns implementation instruments and enforcement mechanisms; and the third concerns institutional structure and governance models. Each criterion was evaluated systematically in terms of implementation capacities and tools, as well as its legal basis.

The study does not limit itself to a textual analysis of the fundamental principles and legal framework of normative legal documents, their implementation mechanisms and sanctions, and their institutional structure and governance differences. In addition to these, the level of alignment of the Law with the Agreement and the EGD, as well as the technical infrastructure, institutional capacity, and depth, were also included in the examination. Thus, beyond identifying legal harmonization and similarities, the study systematically aims to reveal the degree of alignment in implementation instruments and the areas in which shortcomings remain.

The primary data sources for this study were international and national normative legal documents, official websites, and relevant academic studies. The comparative evaluation of positive law texts was conducted by the researcher.

III. Discussion and Results

1. The Legal Framework for the Paris Agreement and the European Green Deal

Paris Agreement is a global agreement that ensures steps are taken toward shared global goals in combating climate change. EGD, on the other hand, is a transformation plan that sets similar goals for the continent but introduces regulations in many areas, from environmental to economic, from social to social structure. Both agreements have legal structures that support and complement each other in pursuit of the same goal.

1.1. Fundamental Principles and Legal Framework of the Paris Climate Accord

The *Paris Agreement* is a legally binding global climate agreement that the entire world has agreed upon and is committed to complying with to combat climate change. The agreement was adopted at COP21 (21st Conference of the Parties) on 12 December 2015, with the participation of 195 countries. It is also the agreement signed in the shortest time possible and became effective on 4 November 2016. The primary aim of the accord is to limit global temperature rise to under 2°C compared to pre-industrial times, and, if possible, to 1.5°C. Its implementation regarding the agreement is carried out through five-yearly updates of the participating countries' Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), which are their nationally planned climate actions, and long-term strategies for low emissions (LT-LEDS). The agreement also requires that industrialized nations offer technological, financial, and capacity-building assistance to developing countries (UNFCCC, 2025).

NDCs, which are among the long-term goals of the Paris Agreement, are the commitments of the party countries to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and combat climate change. According to the agreement, the parties are required to prepare, communicate, and maintain their NDCs in accordance with each country's national capacities and respective capabilities. The Agreement also mandates that, starting in 2020, Parties publicly disclose the main outlines of their NDCs. Collectively, these measures indicate whether the long-term objectives for combating climate change will be achieved, whether greenhouse gas emissions will be reduced to the desired levels, and whether the natural environment can reach an emissions balance. According to the agreement, NDCs must be updated every five years and submitted by the participating country to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) secretariat. It also stipulates that targets should be updated and reported between previous and subsequent NDCs to increase the stated targets. While there is no timeframe for the implementation of NDCs until 2020, they are required to be submitted every five years from 2020 onwards (UNFCCC, 2025).

The Paris Agreement has become an official document that reflects the transition of international climate action to a broader and national level. It has set out the collective national effort on a voluntary basis (Mehling, van Asselt, Das, Droeger, & Verkuyl, 2019, pp.433). The agreement also represents a political consensus that reflects global, multilateral action to combat climate problem. It remains a key international legal document addressing global warming since 1995 *Kyoto Protocol*. In addition global temperature targets, it also sets substantial, though less explicit, targets for climate adaptation and financing. Furthermore, the agreement is the first document to include independent sections on climate adaptation and

funding, technological support, and capacity building, damage as well as losses, and protection for greenhouse gas sinks. It is also the first legal document to include concepts such as the equitable transition of the workforce, indigenous communities' rights, fundamental freedoms, and gender equality, all of which are included in its preamble. The Agreement exhibits a hybrid structure, operating top-down through mechanisms such as compliance procedures and the transparency framework, while functioning bottom-up through instruments like Nationally Determined Contributions to respect state sovereignty. Although the distinction between developed and developing countries was further blurred in the Kyoto Protocol, the principle that developing countries should take a leading role in addressing climate change and support other developing countries has been maintained (Ferreira, 2017, pp. 666–667).

Although the agreement is an international agreement, not all of its provisions impose legal obligations. Participating countries voluntarily set and submit emission reduction targets based on their own national circumstances. They do this through a nationally determined contribution declaration (NDC). Therefore, NDCs are not legally binding in this context (Bodansky, 2021). Paris Agreement, while imposing core obligations on its Parties, takes into account their circumstances and capacities. Instead of punitive sanctions, it incorporates a more facilitative compliance mechanism. In cases of non-fulfilment, transparency is ensured by making this known to all Parties. Moreover, the Agreement does not impose obligations regarding the provision of financial support, specific emission-reduction targets, or any particular climate policy. Therefore, it is a non-punitive instrument that nevertheless places obligations on Parties. It allows for the monitoring of progress made in combating climate change and for transparent reporting (Lewis & Coinu, 2019, pp. 265–269). As can be seen, if the obligations under the Agreement are not fulfilled or its provisions are neglected, there is no punitive consequence for the parties. Article 13 of the Agreement provides a transparency framework to facilitate compliance based on the parties' capacities and specific circumstances. The transparency framework stipulates that developing countries should implement the framework effectively to address climate action, taking into account their capacities and circumstances, and respecting their national sovereignty without imposing any penal sanctions. On the other hand, it mandated the regular submission of national contribution declarations for greenhouse gas emissions. In cases of dispute, the agreement relied on peaceful resolution, as stipulated in Article 14 of the UNFCCC. This non-binding approach falls short of protecting the rights of more vulnerable nations. This leaves compliance with the agreement to the discretion of the parties (Kaya, 2017, pp. 102-103).

1.2. Fundamental Principles and Legal Framework of the European Green Deal

EGD was presented via the EU dated 11 December 2019 as an comprehensive roadmap for the green transformation required by the Paris Agreement, which targets achieving net-zero emissions by 2050 (EU Presidency, 2024).

The Green Deal constitutes a comprehensive set of policies designed to accomplish the continent's carbon neutrality target within 2050. It produces climate action strategies across all sectors—from agriculture to energy, from sustainable development to finance, and from

transport to industry—based on the principles of equality, just transition, transparency, and precaution (European Council, 2025).

The EGD emerges as an ambitious and comprehensive transformation program, a strategy that decouples economic growth from resource use and pursues net-zero emissions by 2050, extending beyond environmental dimensions to encompass political and social aspects. In this context, public participation and the emphasis on democracy gain significant importance. In fact, the Union's environmental policies date back to the 1970s. While past environmental policies were more technocratic and public participation was secondary, in EGD, elements such as more democratic public participation, just transition, and leaving no one or place behind come to the fore (Buzogány, Parks & Torney, 2025, pp. 138-139).

The implementation tool used by the Consensus to achieve its climate-neutral target is the Fit for 55 initiative, which comprises a set of laws. The main ones include the updated EU ETS, the creation of the CBAM, the Renewable Energy Directive, the Energy Efficiency Directive, and the Social Climate Fund, which assists households as well as SMEs in reducing the financial burdens arising from the ETS. It was established temporarily for the period 2026-2032, primarily from the revenues of the ETS and with support through contributions by member states (Council of the European Union, 2023). The directive on energy efficiency stipulates that member states should reduce energy consumption by 11.7% by 2030 (European Environment Agency, 2024-a). The Renewable Energy Directive sets a target across the Union to achieve 42.5% of energy consumption by 2030 (European Environment Agency, 2024-b).

One of the key tools used by the Consensus to achieve its goals is the *Circular Economy Action Plan*. This plan supports incentives to reduce waste and increase recycling, while also ensuring increased sustainability through efficient use of resources. It also includes the Farm-to-Table Strategy designed to reduce climate-related harms on the agriculture and food sector (Global Law Experts, 2025).

Although the Accord is a comprehensive policy that supports the zero-greenhouse gas target with legally binding commitments, Talenti (2025) argues that scientific and legal examinations should be conducted in addition to its focus on green growth. He states that the application of the precautionary principle is essential to the Accord's goal and growth policies. He states that the legitimacy of the EGD depends on scientific proof of the effectiveness of these goals and policies in combating climate change. Therefore, he argues that its legal framework must be based on solid foundations, otherwise it could lead to annulment lawsuits and objections. Hence, it should be addressed not only in achieving ecological objectives but also regarding the coherence of the commitments made together with the precautionary principle (Talenti, 2025, pp. 464-465).

The Accord, which stands out as a holistic strategy, relies on various legal regulations and legally binding rules to achieve its main objectives. Chief among these is the European Climate Law. The law imposes legal obligations to achieve the goal of greenhouse gas balance by 2050. The law, together with the EU Taxonomy Regulation, ensures that economic activities are compatible with natural systems by establishing legal conditions. These practices, by

introducing legal regulations, ensure that environmental policies are implemented more effectively and securely, ensure compliance by the participating countries, and increase their binding effect (European Institute for International Law and International Relations, 2021).

As can be seen, the Accord imposed responsibilities on member states by introducing legal regulations such as the European Climate Law to achieve its objectives. If member states fail to comply with these obligations, it empowers the European Commission, designated as the guardian of the agreements, to initiate infringement proceedings. Furthermore, the European Court of Justice can also impose sanctions such as fines. Because the Accord boasts widespread participation, it even grants citizens the right to file lawsuits in the event of a negative experience (Ole & Anagu, 2025, pp. 7-8).

1.2.1. The Binding Implementation Mechanisms for the European Green Deal: CBAM along with ETS

The European Union Emissions Trading System is a system with the world's pioneering and biggest carbon trading market, under which polluters are required to pay for the greenhouse gas emissions they release. The system covers 40% of the total emissions within the Union and its scope has been significantly expanded to include thermal energy production, electricity, high-energy sectors and air transport, and, most recently in 2024, sea transportation. As part of the Fit for 55 initiative, significant reform steps were taken between 2021 and 2023, including increasing the system's targets, revising aviation regulations and reporting rules for greenhouse gas emissions in maritime transport, incorporating small industries such as road transport and buildings into the ETS, establishing a Social Climate Fund, and implementing the CBAM. Furthermore, while the proceeds obtained by the System are planned to be allocated for financing green transformation, they are also considered a tool for achieving climate action goals over the extended period (European Commission, 2025).

The System, the binding regulation of the EGD, is expected to be strengthened by *Directive 2003/87/EC*. The EU ETS is an economics-based mechanism concerning climate and energy legislation. Legal regulations were enacted for European Union ETS with the aim of preventing emissions relocation and maintaining carbon pricing at socially acceptable levels (Schlacke, Wentzien, Thierjung, & Köster, 2022, pp. 4). The primary objective of the Directive, functioning as the legal foundation of the system, is to ensure cost-effective and efficient cuts in climate-warming emissions and with the purpose of incentivizing successful attainment toward this goal. Alongside its core aim of curbing climate-warming discharges, the scheme also possesses secondary objectives, including ensuring economic efficiency, reducing costs, prioritizing fair implementation, and being consistent with other policies. While the EU ETS does not strictly adhere to a hierarchy of objectives from a legal perspective, a review of the general principles within EU law and the case law from the Court of Justice demonstrates that its priority is toward curbing global-warming emissions. This framework provides the mechanism with legal credibility and enhances its applicability (Kotzampasakis & Woerdman, 2024, pp. 317-333).

Another binding regulatory instrument, CBAM, is the most important tool for implementing the Union's climate strategies. Its main purpose of CBAM is in order to prevent carbon leakage resulting from shifting production to regions with more flexible environmental policies, so as to preserve the competitive strength of Union countries, and with the aim of cutting global discharges (Zhong & Pei, 2023, pp. 229). CBAM is a mechanism that imposes a financial obligation by setting a carbon cost equivalent to that applied within the EU to producers in its own market, calculated from the release levels from goods brought into the Union at the final end within their production stages. In this way, it aims to both act in line with climate policy objectives and prevent unfair competition in the global market. Initially, it covers sectors with high-emission production, including iron and steel, cement, aluminium and electricity, fertilizer, plus hydrogen. The implementation is planned in two phases. In the first phase, the initial stage spanning from Oct 1, 2023, to Dec 31, 2025, importers are only responsible for reporting the embodied emissions in imported products. There is no financial obligation. Starting January 1, 2026, during the full implementation phase, there will be a financial obligation. Importers must obtain CBAM certificates corresponding to the releases they report (European Union, 2023).

The European Commission adopted CBAM Regulation 2023/956 in May 2023 and entered into force in October 2023. Therefore, it is directly applicable in Member States and does not require transposition into national legislation. The Union's attractive internal market, capacity and regulatory power, market competition, and environmental and climate policies, known as the Brussels Effect, inevitably shape global markets (Otto, 2025, pp. 178-180). The regulation of the mechanism has also been prepared in line in accordance with World Trade Organization (WTO) regulations as well as the Union's global legal commitments. It is based on core principles such as proportionality, non-discrimination, environmental sustainability, and transparency. The mechanism operates in coherence with the EU ETS, and as of 2026, the no-cost permits within the ETS will be systematically removed. An requirement to purchase certificates for embedded emissions will be imposed on importing companies within the Union, to ensure equality in carbon pricing between those producing within and outside the Union. For the transition period, only reporting and certificate submission obligations are envisaged, followed by legal financial obligations after 2026. It is stated that administrative sanctions may be applied in case of non-compliance with these obligations (Dobson, 2022, pp. 178-179).

2. Fundamental Principles and Legal Framework of Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552

Climate Law No. 7552 is the first framework law that legalizes Turkey's national regulations and strategies to combat climate change. It entered into force upon publication in the Official Gazette No. 32951 dated July 9, 2025. The law is crucial for transposing Turkey's obligations following its adoption of the Paris Agreement into national law. With the Climate Law, Turkey has ensured that the regulations and implementation tools to be implemented to achieve its 2053 net-zero emissions target, set forth in the National Contribution Declaration, have legal status in national legislation. The law includes key issues such as compliance with

international climate change mitigation, greenhouse gas emission reduction, implementation tools, institutional structure definitions, and criminal sanctions. Most importantly, it establishes the infrastructure for the ETS mechanism, which is effective in international trade (LBF Partners, 2025).

The Turkey Climate Law is based on climate justice, prudence, equality, participation, transparency, integration, just transition, progress, and sustainability, taking into account the concept of shared yet differentiated responsibilities and proportional capacities embodied in UNFCCC and the Paris Agreement. Public institutions, individuals, and legal entities are held accountable for the timely fulfillment and implementation of their obligations, prioritizing the public interest. The law stipulates that progress towards the net-zero emissions target, as outlined in the country's National Contribution Declaration, and towards emission reduction activities will be monitored annually, taking into account development priorities and specific circumstances. Furthermore, the Climate Change Presidency is authorized to ensure coordination among institutions, organize the market mechanism for carbon pricing, determine the necessary standards, activities, information, documents, and data, request them free of charge, and share this information through the Geographic Information Platform application. Public institutions, legal entities, and individuals are obligated to develop, implement, cooperate with, and support projects and plans within their responsibilities and authorities (Official Gazette, 2025). The law mandates climate action aligned with the net-zero targets presented as commitments in the NDC as part of compliance activities. In this regard, it holds public institutions and organizations accountable for combating climate change within national and municipal frameworks. It encourages approaches such as water resource management, increasing biodiversity, ecosystem protection, and sustainable land and sink management. It also emphasizes the need for preventing climate-related damage, reducing disaster losses, integrating early warning systems, and environmentally friendly solutions (Climate Change Laws of the World, 2025).

The law, with its goals and principles, is founded on the right to a healthy living environment as enshrined in Turkey's Constitution and on international agreements. Furthermore, alongside the national ETS and carbon market as implementation tools, there are plans within both national and municipal frameworks. At the central national level, it envisages the preparation of National Climate Change Strategies and Action Plans, while within municipalities, it envisages the development of Local Climate Change Action Plans under the leadership by provincial governors and municipalities. The law includes financial implementation tools. These are the establishment and implementation of the Turkey Taxonomy. It also emphasises the development of incentives to increase investment in green transformation and combating climate change, as well as the support of mechanisms for the circular economy and zero-waste targets. It also states that a CBAM may be established to cover embedded carbon gases in imported products. Technologically, the development of clean technologies, particularly in vehicles, is also targeted. Furthermore, within the scope of climate action, it is envisaged that institutes and research and application centres could be established, and within this framework, curricula and training programmes could be updated to raise social awareness and train a green workforce (Kılınç Law & Consultancy, 2025).

The law is also consistent with the requirements of the EGD. The law has become an important instrument of transformation not only regarding ecological protection but also concerning economic, trade, and industrial policies. The revenues generated during this process are secured by ensuring they can only be used for climate action and green transformation projects. The penalties specified in the law, the clearly defined supervisory powers, and the existing legal remedies have strengthened the functioning and enforceability of the system. Administrative sanctioning powers have been granted to the Climate Change Presidency (Legislative Monitoring, 2025).

3. The Compliance Analysis of the Turkey Climate Law No. 7552 in relation to the Paris Agreement and the European Green Deal

The protection of nature and the implementation of environmentally friendly policies across the world are relatively new developments. Climate change has been recognized as a shared challenge that concerns all nations. For this purpose, countries have, at different periods, signed treaties, protocols, and agreements, and have even enacted laws. Although the degree of binding force, scope, and enforcement of these measures varies, the overarching objective has been to leave a livable world for coming generations.

3.1. Compliance Analysis of Turkey's Climate Law with the Paris Agreement

It would be appropriate to assess the alignment between Turkey's Climate Law and the Paris Agreement by dividing the analysis into two sub-sections.

3.1.1. Fundamental Principles and Legal Framework

- *The Paris Agreement* is an international agreement aimed at combating climate change. Nearly the entire world has participated. Parties voluntarily commit to reducing their emissions through NDCs. While internationally binding, there are no penalties for non-compliance with the NDCs. Parties are required to update their declarations every five years, demonstrating further improvements in their emissions reduction rates compared to the previous year. *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552*, however, is a national law, not an international one. It has established a binding framework for climate action by integrating provisions of international law into national law. Duties and authorities have been defined for institutions and organizations to meet the 2053 net-zero greenhouse gas emission target, as stated in the country's National Contribution Declaration. Penalties are also imposed for non-compliance with the law's provisions. Furthermore, it also requires the formulation of a National Climate Change Strategy and Action Plans within the national framework.

- *The Paris Agreement* encompasses elements such as adaptation, financing, green technology, capacity-building support, and the protection of greenhouse gas sinks in combating climate change. It also incorporates universal concepts such as equality, just transition, and human rights. The climate response is being implemented within a framework of transparency and common but differentiated responsibilities, tailored to the national circumstances of developing countries. *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552*, similar to the Paris Agreement, is based on principles such as equality, just transition, and climate justice, while also emphasizing the principles of adaptation activities, financing, technological progress and

capacity enhancement, shared yet distinct responsibilities, along with respective abilities. However, the Law differs by focusing more on principles such as environmental sustainability and development, rather than broad social concepts such as human rights and gender equality.

- *The Paris Agreement* is a legal document with a mixed structure in terms of hierarchy, being both top-down and bottom-up. *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552* has a centralised top-down structure in that it is based on international agreements. Furthermore, although the participation of provincial administrations, municipalities, and the private sector in the decision-making process is limited, there is also a bottom-up process.

- *According to the Paris Agreement*, in the event of a dispute, peaceful resolution is preferred in accordance with Article 14 of the UNFCCC. *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552*, on the other hand, specifies judicial recourse in the event of a dispute and grants the right to file a lawsuit against the Climate Change Presidency in administrative courts.

- *The Paris Agreement* contains a reporting obligation regarding the expenditure of financial assistance offered by industrialized nations to emerging economies. However, there is no provision stipulating that this support must be spent solely on climate action. *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552* clearly states that revenues generated from climate change mitigation efforts must be spent solely within this framework.

3.1.2. Implementation Tools and Sanctions

- *The Paris Agreement*, as an implementation tool, envisages that the NDCs, which are long-term goals, will be updated by the signatory countries every five years. This is carried out through extended low-carbon development plans with an transparency framework, financial and support mechanisms. *In Turkey's Climate Change Law No. 7552*, the Climate Change Presidency is authorised to coordinate between institutions and to determine and share information and data using the Geographic Information Platform application.

- The Paris Agreement, within its transparency framework, requires parties to regularly report and monitor information, but there are no penalties for failure to do so. *Turkey, under Climate Law No. 7552*, is obligated to share data when the Climate Change Presidency requests information for the Geographic Information Platform application.

- *The Paris Agreement* is an intergovernmental agreement that states may, if they choose, incorporate into their domestic laws and disseminate to the public. *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552*, however, places responsibilities on individuals, companies, and public institutions, holding them accountable for the development, implementation, and management of projects and plans.

- *The Paris Agreement* does not directly address commercial applications such as the CBAM or ETS. However, *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552* mentions the establishment of commercial mechanisms such as both the ETS and the CBAM.

- *The Paris Agreement's* financial mechanisms are primarily driven by developed countries providing support to developing countries. Turkey plans to establish the Turkey Green Taxonomy under *Climate Law No. 7552* to guide and facilitate investments in

combating climate change. It also envisions conducting studies and developing support mechanisms for the circular economy and zero-waste practices.

- While the *Paris Agreement* mentions financial support for developing technological infrastructure and capacity and raising awareness, *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552* focuses on monitoring new technological developments and establishing and developing partnerships in this field. On the other hand, it calls for the establishment of institutes and application and research centres to raise awareness, and for national education and higher education institutions to update their curricula and training to cultivate a green workforce.

- *The Paris Agreement* does not provide for criminal sanctions if the countries parties do not meet the objectives to which they have committed, according to their own national capacities and conditions. In *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552*, however, the penalties for administrative sanctions, the authority for supervision and sanctions, the application and collection of penalties, and legal remedies are clearly specified.

3.2. Compliance Analysis of Turkey's Climate Law with the EU's Green Deal

This analysis regarding Turkey Climate Law and the EGD is also evaluated under two separate headings.

3.2.1. Fundamental Principles and Legal Framework

- *Europe's Green Deal* serves as a framework which sets out the essential requirements outlined by the Paris Agreement on efforts to address global warming. *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552* ensures that measures to tackle global warming are reflected in domestic law as a national law.

- *Europe's Green Deal* is exhaustive transformation guide covering not only environmental policies but also political and social policies and strategies, with emission targets and resource-independent economic growth. It is highly democratic and prioritises public participation. Although *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552* contains provisions on greenhouse gas emission reduction, circular economy, and sustainable development, it lacks regulations concerning social and societal elements.

- The binding foundations under the framework of the *European Green Deal* are listed including the European Climate Law (2021/1119), the EU Taxonomy Regulation, the Fit for 55 program, and the ETS Directive, and the key CBAM legislation. *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552* is based on the requirements outlined by the Paris Agreement and Turkey's Constitution.

- *Europe's Green Deal* is a set of policies based on the principles of equality, just transition, transparency, and precaution, which produces policies to combat climate change in all areas, such as agriculture, energy, sustainable development, sustainable finance, transport, and industry. *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552* is consistent with the principles of the Agreement, such as equality, environmental justice, precaution, participation, sustainability, transparency, and just transition.

- *Europe's Green Deal*, EU ETS, and CBAM revenues will be used to combat climate change. *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552* clearly states that revenues generated from the green transition and resources for addressing climate change will only be spent under this structure.

3.2.2. Implementation Tools and Sanctions

- *Europe's Green Deal* uses the most important implementation tools, namely the EU ETS and CBAM, to achieve its objectives. *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552* is similar in that it states that implementation tools such as investment incentives for climate action, a national ETS, CBAM, and Green Taxonomy will be established.

- *Europe's Green Deal* has a framework that provides legal binding force for the Agreement, which includes key laws such as the Fit for 55 package, the Social Climate Fund, the Directive on Renewable Energy, and the Directive on Energy Efficiency as implementation tools. *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552*, on the other hand, provides for plans both at the national and local scales. At the central level, it envisages the preparation of National Climate Change Strategies and Action Plans, while on the regional/local side, it envisages drafting Local Plans of Action on Climate Change under the leadership by provincial governorships and municipalities.

- While *Europe's Green Deal* lists implementation instruments such as the EU ETS, CBAM, the Action Plan on Circular Economy, and the Farm to Fork Initiative, *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552* outlines measures such as the development of investment incentives for climate action, the establishment of a national ETS, CBAM, and a Green Taxonomy, the enhancement of support mechanisms for circular economy targets and zero waste, the advancement of technological development, the establishment of research and practice centers as well as institutes, the strengthening of public awareness regarding capacity-building tools, the raising of public consciousness, and the updating of educational curricula.

- Under *Europe's Green Deal*, criminal sanctions are imposed by member states. If EU countries fail in fulfilling their obligations toward meeting the specified targets, the European Commission may initiate infringement proceedings, and the Court of Justice may impose fines. Under *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552*, criminal sanctions may also be imposed at the level of companies and individuals. The fines specified in the law, the supervisory powers, and the legal remedies are clearly stated, and the mandate to apply administrative penalties has been delegated to the Climate Change Presidency.

- *Europe's Green Deal* lists specific enforcement sanctions under the Union's ETS together with the economic costs arising from CBAM as sanctions. Similarly, *Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552* also includes ETS and CBAM criminal sanctions and financial burdens.

4. The Institutional Structures and Governance Differences of the Turkey Climate Law, Paris Agreement, and European Green Deal

Examining these institutional and governance structures under Paris Agreement and EGD will enable an assessment to be made regarding the extent to which Turkey's Climate

Law complies with international law, the areas in which regulations need to be made in national law, and the direction and evolution of climate strategies.

Looking at the institutional structure of the Paris Agreement, the UNFCCC has established a governing body called the Conference of the Parties to the Paris Agreement (CMA). The CMA supervises the implementation of the Paris Agreement and adopts decisions to ensure its effective application. The CMA Bureau provides guidance on the functioning of organizations and supports this work of administrative bodies, while the UNFCCC Secretariat facilitates essential flow required for information necessary to carry out the obligations under the Agreement and operates under the United Nations. Among the supporting bodies, for instance, the Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice (SBSTA) provides guidance to administrative organs regarding scientific and technological issues, while the Subsidiary Implementation Body (SBI) supports evaluation and oversight concerning the Agreement's enforcement (UNFCCC, 2025). Another body, the Implementation and Compliance Committee under the Paris Agreement (PAICC), was established by this CMA to promote its implementation of and adherence with the obligations of the Agreement, which consists of twelve full and twelve substitute members elected based on equitable geographical representation (UNFCCC, 2022). To manage financial flows, the Paris Agreement utilizes two entities as its funding mechanism, namely the Green Climate Fund (GCF) and the Global Environment Facility (GEF) (ClimateFinance.Org, 2025).

The European Commission is its most important institutional body of the EGD. It serves as the EU's main executive institution. It is in charge of managing the EU budget and policies while also conducting administrative oversight regarding compliance with Union law (Turkey-Europe Foundation, 2022). Another organization, the CINEA agency, was formed on April 1, 2021, for the purpose of implementing the Union's programs to combat climate change. It focuses on programs in energy, nature, transport, climate action, marine fisheries, the environment, and aquaculture (European Commission, 2025). The Commission's DG CLIMA oversees EU's environmental action, ensuring formulating and executing climate initiatives in member states, while also assisting with green financing (Open Access Government, 2023). DG-ENV manages protecting the environment, ensuring a sustainable world for the generations to come, and developing and implementing environmental policies towards climate protection. Its long-term vision includes ensuring a cleaner environment for individuals, protecting biodiversity, and improving ecosystems (Open Access Government, 2025). Another EU-affiliated institution, EIB Group, serves as the EU's leading financial body globally and the world's largest financial institution. It aims to back the EU's environmental action policies. Providing development financing and assisting with global climate challenges are among its responsibilities (European Investment Bank, 2025, pp.3).

In the institutional structure of Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552, the Ministry responsible for Environment, Urban Planning, and Climate Affairs acts as the main rule-making authority, assuming coordination and leadership in climate action. The Climate Change Presidency has been authorized to implement and supervise regulations concerning the conduct of climate action across all sectors, the reduction of emission levels, and the

adaptation to the green transformation. Another institution defined in the Law is the Central Settlement Institution, which will operate as a central clearing house under the Capital Markets Law. The Carbon Market Board is entrusted with determining strategies, policies, and actions related to the national ETS, approving the country's allocation scheme, and deciding on the overall distribution for complimentary emission permits. Another body within this institutional structure is the Advisory Board, which adopts non-binding opinions and recommendations on strategies and actions concerning the national ETS and the international carbon market. In addition to these institutions, local and civil entities also take part in the structure, with provincial administrations and municipalities playing a role in implementation (Official Gazette, 2025).

4.1. Governance Differences

The Paris Agreement, as an international legal instrument encompassing concepts such as climate adaptation, technological capacity, climate finance, just transition, human rights, and gender equality, has pioneered a profound transformation in the governance of global climate action. While the Agreement, with its transparency framework and compliance mechanisms, reflects a top-down approach, the voluntary commitments submitted by Parties through their NDCs—tailored to their capacities and development levels—represent a bottom-up approach. This dual structure establishes a hybrid model. Consequently, the Agreement extends beyond the state level, enabling the involvement of non-governmental actors in climate governance—including community-based organizations, business sector, local governments, as well as labor organizations—thereby creating an more comprehensive structure along with framework for climate initiatives (Kuyper et al., 2018, pp. 4–7).

Europe's Green Deal initiative has been ratified among EU nations as a comprehensive transformation strategy to achieve the continent's climate neutrality. Through EU Climate Legislation, it serves as an enforceable roadmap across member states. With accompanying measures such as the ETS and CBAM, it also carries significant international implications. In terms of governance, the Green Deal adopts a top-down approach through the climate targets and policy instruments defined by the EU in combating climatic action. Conversely the national regulations of EU member states or nations influenced by these targets, such as Turkey, demonstrate a bottom-up governance approach (Karacan, 2025). Through the Green Deal, the EU strengthens its leadership in the green transition not only by binding climate policies for its member states but also by shaping international dynamics through trade policies and bilateral initiatives (Oberthür & Dupont, 2021, pp. 1108–1110).

The Climate Law No. 7552 of Turkey has been designed to ensure alignment and parallelism with the Paris Agreement and the EGD. However, while both regulations have an international legal character, the Law has a national character. The Law clearly defines the administrative structure and its terminology. It identifies the Ministry responsible for Environment, Urban Planning, and Climate Affairs as the main regulatory authority, while delegating responsibilities for implementation, data collection, monitoring, enforcement, and oversight to the Climate Change Presidency. On the other hand, by establishing the Carbon Market Board and the Advisory Board, the Law incorporates multi-stakeholder governance—

including government authorities, private enterprises, and non-governmental organizations—thus enhancing accountability as well as transparency within a legal framework. In particular, the Law grants broad powers of decision-making, monitoring, supervision, and coordination to the Ministry and the Presidency, thereby reinforcing a centralized governance structure (Legislation Monitoring System, 2025). Accordingly, while both the Agreement and European Green Deal adopt an integrated governance model through both top-down and bottom-up approaches, the Law reveals a structural difference by adhering to a more centralized governance approach.

Local governments in Turkey aim to develop joint solutions and share knowledge through participation in international local government networks in the context of climate change mitigation. However, it is observed that the climate action plans prepared by local governments have a very limited impact on the mitigation process. This is due to the insufficient consideration of climate action in local planning stages and the neglect of adaptation processes. In most cases, monitoring and evaluation mechanisms in the plans are either absent or inadequate. Furthermore, administrative, physical, and financial tools for transferring national-level climate policies to local planning and ensuring the connection between them have not been established (Talu et al., 2021, pp. 101–110). In fact, local governments play a leading role in implementing measures such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, utilizing renewable energy, promoting green buildings and spaces, supporting sustainable transportation, managing wastewater, and enhancing infrastructure resilience. Therefore, local governments hold strategic importance in climate policies both as policy developers and implementers, in terms of raising public awareness, ensuring sustainability, guiding the community, and strengthening capacities (Ekinici, 2025, pp. 30–31).

The inconsistencies between Turkey's Climate Law and the Paris Agreement as well as the European Green Deal are clearly evident in Table 1. The Law differs in terms of its legal nature, core principles, implementation instruments, governance model, institutional structure, financing mechanisms, enforcement provisions, and social dimensions.

Table 1- Differences between the Paris Agreement, the European Green Deal, and Turkey’s Climate Law No. 7552

Topic	Paris Agreement	European Green Deal	Turkey’s Climate Law No. 7552
Legal Nature	Non-binding; an international agreement; parties voluntarily commit to emission reductions.	Binding for member states; a strategy enforceable for EU countries; supported by laws and regulations.	Binding at the national level; a national law with enforceable provisions, including penal sanctions.
Scope and Objective	Limit global temperature rise to 1.5°C.	Achieve climate neutrality for the continent by 2050.	Net-zero emissions target by 2053 at the national level.
Core Principles	Equity, just transition, human rights, common but differentiated responsibilities.	Equity, just transition, transparency, precaution; emphasis on human rights.	Very limited emphasis on human rights.
Institutional Structure	International institutions under UNFCCC supervision, such as CMA, PAICC, GCF, GEF.	European Commission, DG CLIMA, DG ENV, CINEA, EIB, and other EU institutions.	Ministry of Environment, Urbanization, and Climate Change; Climate Change Presidency; national institutions.
Governance Model	Hybrid: top-down and bottom-up.	Centralized top-down, but interactive at national and local levels.	Centralized governance
Financing Mechanisms	International support; developed countries provide financial assistance to developing countries.	EU instruments; revenues from EU ETS and CBAM.	National instruments; e.g., local ETS or revenues from fines.
Implementation Tools	NDCs, LT-LEDS, transparency framework, financial and technical support.	EU ETS, CBAM, Fit for 55, Social Climate Fund, and other instruments.	National ETS, Green Taxonomy, Circular Economy Plan, Geographic Information Platform.
Enforcement Mechanisms	No enforcement.	European Commission enforcement for member states.	Enforcement exists; administrative fines
Social Dimensions	Includes human rights, gender equality, and just transition concepts.	Strong emphasis on public participation, just transition, and social equity	Focuses on environmental and sustainable development aspects.

Note: Table created by the author.

IV. Conclusion

With the rapid industrialization and mechanization initiated by the Industrial Revolution, economic development and growth had taken precedence over everything else. As a result, today's states have recognized the necessity of taking action to leave a more livable planet for future generations. Each country, both for this reason and to maintain its position in the global arena, has been taking steps under the framework of climate policies and strategies. Climate action steps that began in the 1970s have now been built upon more solid foundations. In this context, at the international level, the Paris Agreement (2015) and the European Green Deal (2019) stand out, while at the national level, the 2025 Climate Law No. 7552 of Turkey is noteworthy.

Through this study, the overall alignment of Turkey's Climate Law with the Paris Agreement and the European Green Deal (EGD), as well as its relationship with climate policies, has been analyzed. Turkey's Climate Law is generally consistent with the Agreement and the Deal, which are of international and regional character, particularly about the fundamental principles of transparency, traceability, reporting, just transition, participation, equality, and precaution. In addition to these fundamental principles, the Law is also aligned with shared objectives such as reducing global temperature increase, lowering carbon emissions, promoting green transformation, and encouraging the use of renewable energy. From a legal perspective, while the Agreement and the Deal possess an international legal character, the Law constitutes a national legal document. Notably, the Law incorporates the regulation of an ETS into its legal framework, sets a net-zero emission target, establishes carbon markets and the CBAM, allocates carbon revenues for green transformation, and introduces data entry and reporting obligations. These elements demonstrate that the Law proceeds in parallel with the voluntary approach of the Paris Agreement and the binding regulations of the EGD. This indicates that the Law is in overall alignment with international legislation within the climate regimes.

In addition to this alignment and parallelism, the Law differs from the Agreement and the Deal in governance and structural aspects. The Paris Agreement exhibits a top-down approach through its transparency framework and compliance mechanisms, while its Parties' NDCs create a bottom-up component, resulting in a hybrid governance structure. Participation extends from the state level to communities, encompassing multiple layers. The European Green Deal presents a top-down governance model through its targets and implementation instruments, while also demonstrating a multi-layered bottom-up approach that includes member states and, due to external policy considerations, domestic and regional levels alongside private actors. In contrast, Turkey's Climate Law differs from both the Agreement and the Deal in that decision-making mechanisms are concentrated at the Ministry level, and the limited participation of local governments and civil society results in a more centralized, top-down governance structure.

The study reveals that while the Turkish Climate Law demonstrates overall alignment with the Paris Agreement and the EGD, it achieves partial rather than full compliance within the framework of legal harmonization theory. The Law shows a certain degree of alignment—though not identical—in implementation instruments such as the ETS, reporting, and monitoring. However, it has not reached a full level of compliance in terms of governance structure and institutional capacities. Within the framework of Europeanization theory, it appears that Türkiye needs to harmonize its national legislation to the desired level, particularly in areas where it lacks adequate institutional, governance, and capacity structures.

On the other hand, although the Law establishes the legal framework for the national ETS and the Carbon Market, it has not yet been implemented, similar to the ETS in the EU. Furthermore, with the full enforcement of CBAM in 2026, concrete steps must be taken to avoid economic costs and initiate action. While the Law mentions the establishment of CBAM, it is not yet operational in practice. All of these factors pose significant risks in terms of market stability and transparency. Unlike the Paris Accord and the EGD, the Law explicitly specifies the punitive sanctions to be applied if institutions and organizations fail to fulfill their responsibilities. It also clearly states that the revenues generated will be used exclusively for green transformation. Although the two legal instruments provide flexibility and binding mechanisms, punitive sanctions and the specific allocation of revenues are not clearly defined.

If Turkey cannot establish an institutional structure as robust as the EU's regarding financing needs, skills development, technology sharing, and societal awareness, it is inevitable that difficulties will arise in the implementation phase. By legally embedding the 2053 net-zero emission target, the Law elevates climate action to a legal dimension and encompasses not only environmental aspects but also finance, trade, and green transformation. However, despite this comprehensive approach, the Law remains more limited compared to the EU, and does not provide an integrated framework covering all sectors. Moreover, its implementation measures are not specified in as much detail as the EU standards.

Looking ahead, ensuring participation in decision-making processes from local governments to civil society organizations within the governance structure of the Law, similar to the Green Deal, would further strengthen its holistic approach. Governance that engages all sectors of society, along with the private sector and academia, would facilitate the dissemination and societal integration of the Law. The rapid operationalization of the ETS and CBAM in alignment with EU standards, the optimal functioning of these mechanisms, and the enhanced efficiency of the carbon market would reduce commercial risks. Revenues generated from climate action, when allocated to areas lacking in green transformation—such as technology transfer, capacity building, and just transition—would further strengthen the Law both theoretically and in practice.

Turkey's Climate Law No. 7552 demonstrates overall legal alignment with international normative legal instruments. It constitutes a legal proof of commitment to combating climate change. Through the implementation of the ETS and the conditions of the carbon market, the Law will accelerate emission reductions across sectors. This will strengthen Turkey's trade competitiveness in both the EU and global markets. Adopting a more inclusive and

comprehensive approach in the institutional and governance domains will indicate Turkey's active participation in international climate action. The Climate Law is a positive step and an opportunity for the green revolution.

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